

Case Series

Exploring health system barriers to paediatric leukaemia care at a tertiary hospital in Northeast Nigeria: a case series

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Abstract

Background: Children with leukaemia in low- and middle-income countries face survival disparities largely attributable to health system deficiencies. These barriers remain poorly characterised in conflict-affected regions. This study describes health system barriers to paediatric leukaemia care at a tertiary hospital in Northeast Nigeria, using the WHO Health System Building Blocks framework. **Materials and methods:** We reviewed all confirmed paediatric leukaemia cases (N=10) managed at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi (January 2023–December 2025). Three cases were purposively selected to illustrate distinct barriers: a child with B-acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) and hyperleukocytosis, an adolescent with B-ALL experiencing treatment abandonment, and a child with chronic myeloid leukaemia (CML). Data were abstracted from medical records using a standardised tool, with barriers mapped to the six WHO building blocks. **Results:** Barriers were identified across all six blocks: prolonged diagnostic intervals (median 5.2 months) and fragmented referrals (service delivery); low cancer awareness and diagnostic overshadowing (health workforce); reliance on morphology alone and centralized molecular testing requiring 500 km travel with 50-day delay (health information systems); chemotherapy stockouts and unreliable blood products (essential medicines); catastrophic out-of-pocket expenditures costing up to three months' household income (financing); and absence of a childhood cancer registry (leadership/governance). Despite these constraints, all three patients achieved morphologic remission or hematologic response through family engagement and protocol modifications. **Conclusions:** Paediatric leukaemia outcomes in Northeast Nigeria are constrained by interconnected health system failures across all WHO building blocks. Targeted investments in diagnostics, essential medicines, financial protection, and governance are urgently needed.

Keywords: Conflict-affected health systems, Health system barriers, Nigeria, Paediatric leukaemia, Treatment abandonment;

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Introduction

Paediatric acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) is the most common childhood malignancy in Nigeria, with studies documenting typical presentations of fever, pallor, and organomegaly.^{1,2} Chronic myeloid leukaemia (CML), while less frequent, poses distinct management challenges due to its requirement for targeted therapy and molecular monitoring.^{3,4} Nigeria's estimated childhood cancer incidence of 100–150 per million children annually suggests 4,000–6,000 new cases each year, though the absence of a national registry likely underestimates the true burden.⁵ Treatment outcomes for paediatric leukaemia in Nigeria remain poor, with high rates of treatment abandonment and mortality.^{6,7} While complete remission rates of 70–85% have been reported among patients completing induction at Nigerian centres, long-term survival lags at 30–50%, compared to >85% in high-income countries (HICs).^{8,9} This survival gap is increasingly understood to be a consequence of

health system deficiencies rather than of disease biology alone.¹⁰ The World Health Organisation's (WHO) health system framework identifies six interconnected building blocks that determine health system performance: service delivery, health workforce, health information systems, access to essential medicines, financing, and leadership/governance.¹¹ Deficiencies in these domains create cascading barriers along the cancer care continuum.

In Nigeria's decentralised health system, patients must navigate primary health centres, general hospitals, and tertiary facilities, each with varying capacity for the recognition and management of childhood cancer.¹² Northeast Nigeria faces additional challenges: prolonged armed conflict has displaced over two million people, disrupted health infrastructure, restricted transportation, and eroded an already fragile health workforce.¹³ These contextual factors likely amplify barriers documented in other low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

This study aims to: (1) describe health system barriers encountered in the diagnosis, treatment, and supportive care of paediatric leukaemia patients at a tertiary hospital in Northeast Nigeria; (2) map these barriers to the WHO health system building blocks; (3) identify context-adaptive strategies employed by clinicians and families; and (4) generate hypotheses about potential intervention points for health system strengthening.

Materials and methods

Study Design and Setting

We conducted a retrospective case series at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi, Northeast Nigeria. ATBUTH is a 550-bed tertiary referral centre serving Bauchi State (population approximately 8 million) and surrounding states. The hospital has one paediatric oncologist (the first author) and receives referrals from primary health centres, general hospitals, and private clinics across the region.

Sampling Frame and Case Selection

All children (<18 years) with suspected haematologic malignancies evaluated at ATBUTH between 1 January 2023 and 31 December 2025 were identified from paediatric oncology records, admission registers, and haematology laboratory logs. During these 36 months, 27 children were evaluated for suspected haematologic malignancy. Of these, 10 had confirmed leukaemia based on bone marrow morphology (ALL, n=9) or

morphology plus molecular testing (CML-chronic phase, n=1).

From the 10 confirmed cases, we purposively selected three cases for in-depth analysis. Selection criteria prioritised: maximum variation across diagnoses, age groups, and clinical presentations; illustrative richness regarding specific health system barriers; data completeness (>80% of key variables); and follow-up duration (minimum 6 months). The three selected cases represent distinct barrier patterns: (1) acute presentation and supportive care challenges (ALL with hyperleukocytosis); (2) referral fragmentation and financial toxicity leading to abandonment (ALL with reinduction after default); and (3) molecular diagnostic access barriers (CML).

Data Collection and Analysis

A standardised data abstraction tool was developed based on a literature review and the WHO Health System Building Blocks framework. Two investigators (UAS, MA) independently abstracted data from medical records; discrepancies were resolved through discussion with the third investigator (AFS). Inter-rater reliability was strong ($\kappa = 0.84$).

Data were analysed descriptively. For the three selected cases, narrative summaries followed a standardised structure: presentation and diagnostic pathway, key barriers mapped to WHO building blocks, adaptive strategies employed, and outcome.

Ethical Considerations

The ATBUTH Health Research Ethics Committee approved this study (ATBUTH/HREC/2025/042). A waiver of informed consent was granted for this retrospective chart review. To protect patient privacy, we removed all direct identifiers, used age ranges rather than specific ages, omitted potentially identifying clinical details, and presented socioeconomic information in aggregate where possible.

Results

Cohort Characteristics

Among the 10 confirmed leukaemia cases, the median age was 7 years (range 1.5–16). The male-to-female ratio was 1.5:1. Patients travelled a median of 187 km (range 15–420) to reach ATBUTH. Median symptom duration before presentation was 4 months (range 1–8). Patients visited a median of 3 healthcare facilities (range 1–6) before reaching ATBUTH.

Among the 9 ALL patients: 4 (44%) experienced treatment abandonment (≥ 4 weeks missed treatment¹⁴); 3 (33%) died during treatment; 2 (22%) died before treatment initiation. Among treated

ALL patients (n=7), 5 (71%) achieved morphologic remission. The single CML patient achieved hematologic response on imatinib.

Selected Case Summaries

Table 1 presents key characteristics of the three selected cases.

Table 1: Characteristics of Selected Cases

Characteristic	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Age (years)/Sex	4-5/F	14-16/F	7-9/M
Diagnosis	B-ALL	B-ALL	CML-CP
Symptom duration (months)	2	6	3
Facilities visited	2	4	3
Time to diagnosis (days)	3	5	50*
Treatment interruptions†	3 episodes	2 episodes	1 episode
Follow-up (months)	12	18	6
Status	Morphologic remission	Morphologic remission	Hematologic response

*Includes 20 days fundraising and 30 days awaiting batched PCR transport
 † >1 week delay in scheduled therapy

Case 1: Diagnostic Misdirection and Supportive Care Challenges

Presentation: A girl aged 4–5 years presented with two months of fever and generalised oedema, followed by two weeks of dyspnea and one week of oliguria. A peripheral hospital suspected renal disease and referred her to nephrology. Three days after admission, she developed respiratory distress; CBC revealed leukocytes 350,000/mm³ (88% blasts), confirming ALL with hyperleukocytosis and tumour lysis syndrome.

Barriers by WHO Block:

- **Service Delivery:** Referring facility lacked CBC capability; 3-day delay in obtaining

CBC due to renal framing; febrile neutropenia managed on the general ward without isolation

- **Health Workforce:** Disease-focused triage overlooked malignancy; lack of protocols led to dosing error (prednisolone 40 mg/m² vs. 10 mg/m² for 48 hours)
- **Essential Medicines:** Unreliable transfusion support necessitated shortening the pre-phase from 7 to 5 days

Adaptive Strategies: Implemented double-check system and pre-printed order sheets; modified protocol (omitted doxorubicin days 8/15; used Capizzi methotrexate).

Outcome: Induction completed over 53 days (vs. standard 28) due to three febrile neutropenia episodes and two funding delays. End-induction bone marrow showed 2% blasts (morphologic remission). At 12 months, she remains on treatment in continued remission.

Case 2: Referral Fragmentation, Financial Toxicity, and Abandonment

Presentation: A girl aged 14–16 years presented with six months of recurrent fever and weight loss, and two weeks of bone pain. She had visited four facilities over six months, receiving treatment for presumed malaria, typhoid, and gastroenteritis. At ATBUTH, examination revealed fever, wasting, lymphadenopathy, and splenomegaly. Five days were spent on TB/HIV testing (both negative) before bone marrow confirmed B-ALL.

Barriers by WHO Block:

- **Health Workforce:** Low cancer awareness at primary level (4 facilities missed diagnosis); diagnostic overshadowing at tertiary level (5-day TB/HIV workup)
- **Service Delivery:** No structured referral pathways; treatment abandonment (≥4 weeks missed) after day 8
- **Financing:** L-asparaginase cost N400,000 (~3 months' income); family unable to purchase
- **Essential Medicines:** L-asparaginase unavailable; blood product shortages required whole blood during cytopenia

Adaptive Strategies: Modified UKALL induction without L-asparaginase; intensive family counselling (3 sessions); extended reinduction (56 days vs. 29).

Outcome: Returned after 3 months with progressive symptoms. Reinduction completed; end-induction bone marrow showed <1% blasts. At 18 months, she remains in remission on consolidation therapy.

Case 3: Molecular Diagnostics and Targeted Therapy Access

Presentation: A boy aged 7–9 years presented with three months of weight loss and abdominal swelling. He had visited three facilities receiving treatment for malaria and "anaemia." Examination revealed massive splenomegaly (14 cm). CBC showed leukocytes $320 \times 10^9/L$; peripheral film confirmed CML-CP.

Barriers by WHO Block:

- **Health Workforce:** Low CML awareness at the primary level (splenomegaly misattributed to malaria over 3 visits)
- **Health Information Systems:** Centralised molecular testing (BCR-ABL only at private lab 500 km away)

- **Service Delivery:** No specimen transport system (family responsible; batched shipping added 30-day delay); imatinib unavailable locally
- **Financing:** Test cost \$200 USD (~2 months' income), out-of-pocket
- **Essential Medicines:** Imatinib unavailable locally; ongoing supply disruptions

Adaptive Strategies: Family fundraising (sold livestock, borrowed); hydroxyurea during 50-day delay; referral to distant centre for imatinib through Max Access Solutions.

Outcome: BCR-ABL confirmed CML-CP (25.9% IS). Achieved hematologic response on imatinib. At 6 months, clinically stable, but local supply remains inconsistent.

Summary of Barriers

Table 2: Health System Barriers by WHO Building Block

WHO Block	Key Barriers	Examples
Service Delivery	Fragmented referrals; no dedicated oncology ward; centralised services	2–4 facilities visited before diagnosis; 500 km travel for testing
Health Workforce	Low cancer recognition, diagnostic overshadowing, and inadequate supervision	4–6 months of malaria/typhoid treatment; dosing error from unsupervised resident
Health Information Systems	Morphology alone; no specimen transport; no registry	All patients receive high-risk protocols; 50-day BCR-ABL delay
Essential Medicines	Chemotherapy stockouts; unaffordable alternatives; blood shortages	L-asparaginase unavailable; transfusion delays; imatinib requires an external program
Financing	Catastrophic out-of-pocket costs; no insurance	L-asparaginase cost = 3 months' income; 81% of cohort sold assets
Leadership/Governance	No registry; decentralised procurement; no regional coordination	No outcome data; Northeast has 0.8 doctors/10,000 vs. national 3.8

Discussion

This case series elucidates health system barriers to pediatric leukaemia care in conflict-affected Northeast Nigeria using the WHO building blocks framework. The three cases reveal how systemic deficiencies across all six domains interact along the care continuum, profoundly shaping outcomes.

All patients experienced prolonged diagnostic intervals (median 5.2 months), consistent with findings from other Nigerian centres (Enugu: 15.7 weeks¹⁵; multicenter data: 4–6 months¹⁶) and across sub-Saharan Africa (Kenya: 3.5 months¹⁷; Tanzania: 4.2 months¹⁸; Uganda: 5.0 months¹⁹). These delays substantially exceed those in HICs (days to weeks).²⁰

Fragmentation—patients navigating 2–4 facilities before tertiary care—reflects absent referral pathways. Only 30% of Nigerian centres have formal referral agreements.²² In Northeast Nigeria, this is exacerbated by geographic barriers (median travel 187 km; some >400 km), road insecurity, and seasonal impassability.

Primary-level misattribution of leukaemia symptoms to endemic infections was critical. Cases 2 and 3 spent 4–6 months receiving treatment for malaria/typhoid before cancer was considered. Only 23% of northern Nigerian primary physicians can identify ≥3 childhood cancer warning signs; 67% have never referred a suspected case.²⁶ Similar findings are reported from Kenya²⁷ and elsewhere.²⁸

At the tertiary level, "diagnostic overshadowing"—prioritising common diseases—delayed Case 2's diagnosis by five days for TB/HIV exclusion. Workforce shortages compound this: Nigeria has ~60 pediatric oncologists for >200 million people (ratio 1:3.3 million children vs. HIC 1:50,000–100,000).²⁹

Reliance on morphology alone, without flow cytometry or cytogenetics, constrains care. All patients received high-risk protocols, potentially exposing lower-risk patients to unnecessary toxicity while failing to intensify therapy for high-risk disease.

Case 3's BCR-ABL testing illustrates the consequences of centralised diagnostics. With one laboratory serving 19 states (500 km distance), patients face 50-day delays—similar to challenges across sub-Saharan Africa.^{33,34} The absence of MRD monitoring means "remission" refers to morphology, which misses low-level disease.³⁶

Chemotherapy stockouts are endemic. A 2022 survey found essential chemotherapeutics unavailable for 4–6 months annually³⁸—consistent with 12-country LMIC data (40% availability).³⁹

Case 2's inability to access L-asparaginase (unavailable; unaffordable at N400,000) meant suboptimal induction and contributed to abandonment. Blood product shortages affected 67% of the cohort; platelets were available within 24 hours for only 35% of requests.⁴¹ For CML, targeted therapy access requires charitable programs; 40% of Nigerian centres report supply disruptions.⁴²

Out-of-pocket payment dominates Nigerian health financing (<5% insured; NHIS excludes informal sector >80%⁴³). In our cohort, 81% sold assets, 89% borrowed, 70% reduced food expenditure. These findings parallel India (\$2,500–5,000 per course; 40% catastrophic expenditure⁴⁴) and Kenya (costs = 2–3 years' income⁴⁵). Abandonment rates of 10–50%

are reported across sub-Saharan Africa,^{46,47} with financial constraints as the primary driver.^{48,49}

Nigeria's National Cancer Control Plan (2018–2022) lacked childhood cancer targets and implementation frameworks.⁵⁰ In contrast, Kenya and Tanzania have stand-alone childhood cancer strategies.^{51,52} Decentralized procurement contributes to stockouts; centralized models (South Africa⁵³, India⁵⁴) improve availability. The absence of a national childhood cancer registry prevents accountability.

Conflict amplifies these barriers: >2 million internally displaced;¹³ displacement disrupts continuity and diverts resources. Geographic isolation (median 187 km; some >400 km) and seasonal road impassability compound challenges. Socio-cultural factors—including traditional healers (Case 2)—reflect limited access and culturally embedded illness models.

Adaptive Strategies and Resilience

Despite barriers, all three patients achieved treatment response through:

- **Family-level adaptations:** Fundraising (Case 3); intensive counselling (Case 2) shown to reduce abandonment by 30–50% in LMIC studies^{57,58}
- **Clinical adaptations:** SIOP PODC-aligned modifications⁵⁹ including agent omission during stockouts (Case 2), alternative regimens (Case 1), and extended treatment duration
- **Health system adaptations:** Daily huddles; pre-printed order sheets; charitable program engagement (Case 3)

These adaptations demonstrate resilience but should not obscure underlying system failures.

Recommendations

Short-term (0–2 years): Red-flag algorithms for primary care; phone consultation service; financial navigation training; paper-based tracking.

Medium-term (2–5 years): Pooled chemotherapy procurement; specimen transport system; advocate for childhood cancer insurance coverage; dedicated oncology beds.

Long-term (5+ years): Regional reference laboratory; mandated national childhood cancer registry; workforce expansion; stand-alone childhood cancer strategy.

This case series cannot establish causation; findings are hypothesis-generating. Purposive selection may introduce bias. Retrospective data depend on record completeness. Follow-up (6–18 months) is insufficient for long-term outcomes. As a single-centre study, generalizability may be limited, though barriers align with LMIC literature.

Key hypotheses warranting investigation: (1) relative contributions to diagnostic delay; (2) safety of task-shifting protocols; (3) cost-effectiveness of sample transport vs. decentralized laboratories; (4) interventions to reduce financial toxicity in humanitarian settings.

Conclusions

This case series demonstrates that pediatric leukaemia outcomes in Northeast Nigeria are constrained by interconnected health system failures across all six WHO building blocks. In the full cohort, 40% abandoned treatment, 30% died during treatment, and 20% died before treatment could begin – outcomes far below the WHO Global Initiative for Childhood Cancer's 60% survival target by 2030.⁶⁰

Achieving this target in conflict-affected regions requires not only clinical excellence but fundamental health system transformations that make the adaptations described here unnecessary for future patients. Short-term actions can begin immediately; medium-term investments require policy engagement; long-term transformations demand sustained commitment. The experiences of these three children illuminate both the distance remaining and the path forward.

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